

The Beautiful System

Numbers and Symbols are interchangeably units, values, or lengths in metres, as appropriate. $\approx$ is “engineering equals” as opposed to mathematical equals =. So 3.14159265... $\approx$ 3.1416.

- $\pi \approx 3.1416$
- $\tau = 2\pi = 6.2832$
- $\phi \approx 1.618$
- $\phi^2 = \phi + 1 = 2.618$
- $e \approx 2.7183$
- $\acute{e} = e - 1 = 1.7183$
- $m = \text{metre} = 1.000$
- $\mathbb{C} = \text{royal cubit} = \pi/6 = 0.5236$
- $f = \text{foot} = \mathbb{C}/\acute{e} \approx 0.30472$
- $Y = \text{“megalithic yard”} = \mathbb{C} + f = 0.82832$
- $M = \text{Grand Metre} = m + \mathbb{C} = 1.5236 = 5 \text{ feet}$
- $S = \text{six feet (fathom)} = m + \mathbb{C} + f = 1.82832$

Figure 1: Circle with 1m diameter.

Figure 2: Seed of Life gives 60°

Figure 3: $m + \mathbb{C} + \phi = \pi$

$$\frac{\pi}{6} = \frac{\phi^2}{5} = \pi - \phi^2 = \mathbb{C} \quad \pi - \phi - \mathbb{C} = m \approx \frac{7\pi}{5\phi e}$$

$$\frac{\pi+1}{e} \approx \frac{\phi^2}{\acute{e}} \left(= \frac{\phi+1}{e-1} \right) \approx \pi - \phi = \mathbb{C} + m = M$$

$$\text{digit} = \frac{52.36}{28} = 1.87 \text{ cm} \approx \frac{\pi\phi}{e}$$

$$\text{(hypothesized) royal inch} = \frac{52.36}{20} = 2.618 \text{ cm} = \phi^2 \text{ cm}$$

$$\text{then royal foot} = 12 \times 2.618 = 31.416 \text{ cm} = 10\pi \text{ cm} = \frac{\mathbb{C}}{1\frac{2}{3}}$$

Figure 4: $\phi^2 + 7\mathbb{C} = \tau$. Clock, zodiac

$$\frac{\mathbb{C}}{f} \approx \frac{e\mathbb{C}}{Y} \approx \frac{\acute{e}}{m} \approx \frac{\phi^2}{M} \approx \frac{\pi}{S} \approx \acute{e} = 1.7183$$

This links the three most famous irrationals: π , ϕ , and e , with three base units of length: **foot**, (royal) **cubit**, and **metre**, and three derived lengths: “**megalithic yard**”, **five feet** (grand metre), and **six feet**, via a consistent ratio of $\acute{e}$.